

Innovative tools for collaborative forest management

Introduction

Wood production, biodiversity conservation, protection against natural risks, public reception for recreational activities, carbon storage... The forest provides multiple services at the origin of sometimes contradictory management issues which can generate conflicts between players. To reconcile all of these issues, the tools available to forestry stakeholders are increasingly numerous: remote sensing, field protocols, models, participatory approaches, etc. If these tools are co-constructed, articulated between them and shared with all stakeholders, they can contribute to the success of sustainable forest management.

Methodology and results

LiDAR technology, Sylvaccess model, diagnosis of the sensitivity of a stand to logging, protocol for characterizing mature forests... So many tools available to stakeholders in the territory and the timber industry to better understand and manage their forests. The OUI-GEF project aimed to help these actors take advantage of these tools and create multi-partner and concerted forest management.

Carried out in three Regional Natural Parks (PNR), OUI-GEF is structured around three specific objectives.

The first consisted of providing a more detailed understanding of the forest resource, its ecosystem services, the behaviour of certain species sensitive to climate change such as spruce or fir, and knowing where the islands of old wood necessary for the preservation of the biodiversity.

The second objective was to identify the conditions for mobilizing the resource (access, slopes, dragging distance) and the potential economic, environmental and social impacts of logging, and to study the behaviour of private forest owners in order to determine their motivations for exploiting their forest.

The third objective aimed to promote the sharing of knowledge between stakeholders, an essential issue to achieve multi-partner and concerted forest management in the territories.

OUI-GEF has resulted in the creation of numerous tools and methods for the benefit of stakeholders and managers, including:

- An innovative method for carrying out a forest inventory, based on LiDAR technology;

- Automatic mapping of the accessibility of forest stands in mountain areas using Sylvaccess software;
- A method for diagnosing the sensitivity of a stand to felling and estimating the effect of the intervention;
- Operational models to map forests with a protective function (avalanches and rockfalls);
- A simplified field protocol to identify mature forests, an essential element of the old woodland network.

An analysis of approaches to valorizing local wood resources which highlights the processes by which the value of local wood is built during the creation of a Wood Energy platform or an AOC (controlled designation of origin).

An online educational game to understand how forest wood, properly managed, transported, stored and burned, can advantageously replace other non-renewable resources to heat our homes.

The challenge for the years to come is to continue the dissemination of tools and the sharing of knowledge resulting from the project. An online geocatalogue to encourage transfer. This geo-referenced metadata base brings together information on the data used by researchers and stakeholders involved in forest management: maps, field surveys, stand analysis grid, etc. It is accompanied by appropriate instructions for concrete issues in order to support the realization of forestry projects.

Lessons learned

OUI-GEF has made it possible to develop operational and transferable tools offering stakeholders and managers the opportunity to better understand forests, their populations, their functions, etc. The active involvement of PNR project managers has encouraged strong mobilization of local stakeholders to participate in tests, respond to surveys and provide feedback on project output

The information presented in this factsheet was developed by the FOREST4EU partner, drawing on the innovations and knowledge generated by the indicated operational group with their explicit authorization.

Further information

<https://www.psd-r.fr/boite-a-outils/filiere-bois-foret>

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